

Ansar-ud-deen Society of Nigeria

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The Ansar-ud-deen Society of Nigeria is a Muslim organisation established in Lagos, Nigeria with a view to developing the Muslim community in terms of education, and enhancing the social and moral development of the Muslims. The organisation was founded in 1923. It is neither a sectarian nor a political educational organisation. In fact, in the typological analysis of Islamic organisations in Nigerian society, Ansar-ud-deen society of Nigeria is considered as one of the first generation Islamic organizations in the country. The establishment of the organisation in question was informed by a response to the advent of a class of Western trained Christian elites in the colonial capital of Lagos. Thus, this organization emerged to engage in the promotion of reformist ideas and development in the Muslim communities of Lagos and later in Nigeria. Today, the society has gone far to the extent that its branches abound in almost every place where Nigerian Muslims are found at home and abroad. In 1926, the society constituted a mission board assigned to organize the religious related activities such as the celebration of some important Islamic events and dates, open-air praying, child naming ceremonies and fund raising programs. The organization has spread all over the towns and cities in Nigeria. And characteristically, any place where the branch is found, there used to be the society's mosque where members would be observing their prayers, particularly the Jum'ah Salah (Friday's prayer) that divinely holds on every Friday in lieu of the Zuhr Salah (afternoon's prayer) that is being observed in any other day. During the service on Fridays, the chief Imam of the branch will lead the congregants by first delivering khutbah (sermon) before the observance of two rak'ahs. The recital from the Quranic passages in the prayer, including the opening chapter of the Quran, will be made aloud- and this is opposed to the manner of recitation during the middle of the day in all other six days of the week. In the Ansar-ud-deen Society, women are active major players. They are being carried along with all the organizational activities. The society has a women's wing, whereby the majority of the wives of the members too play a vital role in the religious propagation and obligations among their fellow women in the society. As a matter of fact, the women's role is spiritual and material. They engage in a prayer session called Asalātu on Sundays, and make a financial contribution which is of material benefit to the development of the society. Both the men and the women fundraise for the society's coffer. The funds generated through the members' contribution is being used to run the affairs of the society which include, among other things, building of mosques and madāris (Arabic/ Islamic schools), sponsorship of many dawah programs through the mass media and so on.

Date Range: 1923 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa. Most Nigerian Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: West Africa and Islam by Peter B. Clarke
- Source 2: Andrew Roberts. The Colonial Moment in Africa: Essays on the Movement of Minds and Materials, 1900-1940, Cambridge University Press, 1990.
- Source 3: Stefan Reichmuth. 'Education and the Growth of Religious Associations among Yoruba Muslims: The Ansar-Ud-Deen Society of Nigeria', Journal of Religion in Africa > Vol. 26, Fasc. 4 (Nov., 1996), pp. 365-405.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1570982>
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/154374097922439/>
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.summituniversity.edu.ng/>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://www.bowcentralmosque.co.uk/ansar_ud_deen.html
- Source 1 Description: Bow Central Mosque Schedule of Activities
- Source 2 URL: https://www.bowcentralmosque.co.uk/ansar_ud_deen.html
- Source 2 Description: <https://litcaf.com/>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the Ansar-ud-deen members still belong to some other religious orders like Tijaniyyah and Quadriyyah orders of Sufism. They believe all these groups are only seeking ways of getting the pleasure of the only one God through their prayer fora and dawah programs, for the Quran remains their general divine Scripture and the Ka'bah is the Qiblah while observing prayers. All the groups are associated with the Islamic monotheism.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Any person who believes in the statement of declaration 'Lailaha illa Allah, Muhammad rasulLah' (None deserves to be worshiped except Allah, and Muhammad was His Messenger) is qualified to join the organization irrespective of age, gender and status in the society.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Many people have been converted to Islam through the many activities and programs of the

organization at home and abroad.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: This religious organization is apolitical. Members have their rights to vote for the candidates of their choice, and not influenced by the leadership of the society. This is because the leadership had foreseen that politics does more harm than good as far as the Nigerian society is concerned. Thus, if the society has been politically inclined right from its establishment, it would have crumbled.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group only tries to preach to those who renounce the Islamic monotheism and convinces them with the Islamic guidelines contained in the Quran and Sunnah of the Prophet of Islam. If the apostates fail to revert, no harm is done to them.

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Qur'an and Hadith which are considered as the two primary sources of Islamic guidelines are the scriptures followed by the adherents. When they quote the Quranic verses,

they refer to the Hadith which underpins and explains the messages contained in the Qur'an that tend to be ambiguous. For instance, the Qur'an commands the Muslims to observe Salat, but the details regarding the how of Salat and its timing could be traceable to the Prophetic traditions.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an was revealed to the Prophet of Islam orally, but later documented in order not to get lost. The Prophet committed the whole Qur'an to memory and many other people among his companions. This practice will continue for ever because Qur'an is meant to be recited and memorized. The formal compilation of Qur'an took place during the reign of the first Caliph in Islam, Abubakr as-Siddiq. What led to the compilation was the martyrdom of many Qur'an memorizers among the companions during the wars of apostasy. The Sunnah of the Prophet formed his Hadith. This was also initially oral, but later documented so that generations of Muslims would continue to have access to it in the passage of time.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) who was the recipient of the Qur'an used to frequently go to the cave of Hira in Mecca, where he used to meditate on the creatures of Allah and appreciate the almighty Allah for His wonderful creation. One day, the arch angel appeared unto him and ordered him to read. He to the angel: " I am unlettered". The angel repeated the commanding statement , and the prophet also repeated the answer. Until third time, the angel said: "read in the name of thy Lord, the One Who created He created man from the clot...". The first five verses of the chapter 96 then marked the dawn of the Quranic revelation to the Prophet of Islam. Later, the revelation of the whole Qur'an was taking place piece-meal. It took 23 years before the complete Quranic revelation was made, 13 years in Mecca and its vicinity , and 10 years in Madinah and its environs.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Is iconography present:

– I don't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Yes, when a believing person is alive his/her life is precious and should be preserved and not harmed. However, when he/she becomes dead the corpse of the deceased should be buried according to Islamic rite. The burial arrangement should not be unnecessarily delayed. And the use of flamboyant and sophisticated materials for burial is forbidden. Decoration of the grave is Islamically unethical, and holding a party in honor of the deceased is considered as an outrage, according to the Islamic guidelines.

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:
- I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

- Yes

Notes: Among the articles of faith in Islam is the belief in afterlife. Death is just a transition from the surface of earth to another life inside the earth (grave). A person buried is experiencing another life in the grave and till the resurrection and judgement day.

Reincarnation in this world:

- No

Notes: According to Islamic guidelines, reincarnation is not recognized. The phenomenon is not somewhat ambiguous and tends to adulterate and weaken one's faith. Of what benefit will the reincarnation of a deceased person to the family of the deceased? Reincarnation is believed to have been a mastermind of the devil to make the believers degenerate spiritually.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

- Yes

Notes: When a Muslim devotee has passed on, the fellow Muslims shall wash him/her, shroud him/her with white perfumed cloths, and observe Salat (prayer) on his/her corpse. This will be done to testify to and complement his/her devotion while living on the earth. It is forbidden to step or sit on the grave. This means that the life of the fellow in the grave is as good as being alive. This Islamic practice is what the members of the organization uphold as Muslims availing themselves of Quranic injunctions and Prophetic traditions.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

- No

Are grave goods present:

- No

Are formal burials present:

- Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: The corpse of the deceased Muslim should be buried in the public cemetery of the Muslim community. This is preferable.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: The formal burial is made by digging the grave for the deceased in the public cemetery of the Muslims, and the internment of the corpse will be made after the ritual bath of the deceased, shrouding with white cloths perfumed, and Salat observed on him/her. That is all. No decoration of the grave with the sophisticated modern materials should be made, and the use of the coffin is not in line with the Islamic guidelines.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings are angels charged with the custody of the grave and its occupant. Belief in this phenomenon is part of Islamic doctrinal values.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

– No

– No

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The Supreme high God is invisible

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high God has the knowlegde of all human non-human phenomena existing in this world

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are the angels charged with the custody of the corpse buried.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Done to identify the disobedient servants of God

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - No
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– I don't know

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: According to Islamic guidelines, there is punishment for the evildoers right from the afterlife, where the righteous ones will be rewarded with enjoyment of pleasure right from their eschatological life.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

- No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

- Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

- No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

- Yes

Notes: There should not be an engagement in the sexual intercourse with one's legal couple during the day while one is observing fasting, particularly compulsory fasting of the month of Ramadan.

- ↳ Monogamy (males):
 - No

- ↳ Monogamy (females):
 - No

Notes: Female is not allowed to have many sexual partners.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Homosexuality is forbidden.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Lesbianism is proscribed.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Except the fasting of the prescribed month (Ramadan) and recommended days according to the Prophetic traditions.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– I don't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: My brothers and sisters in Islam

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: Our elders in Islam

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Yes

Notes: Obedient servants of Allah, our fathers and mothers in Islam.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: This is done through the Zakat revenues generated and the society's treasury

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: the members tend to enjoy the famine relief from other religious bodies and organizations since the Muslims are brethren irrespective of their organizational affiliations.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: This is done through Zakat, and at the individual level among the members. Those with deep pockets help the poverty-stricken ones among the members of the organization. This practice is synonymous with the Islamic injunctions on the act of kindness and generosity.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: This is done by soliciting a financial aid from the members that are with deep pockets.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through the solicitation of financial assistance from the men of substance who do not formally belong to the religious group on the basis of brotherhood.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: It is non-commercial.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, government does provide transportation infrastructure to the citizenry without religious, tribal, gender and class discriminations.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, this is done in the name of financial assistance and made voluntary.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, to provide them security whenever they are having public program.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The general Islamic institutionalized punishments are what the members recognize although they may not be fully implemented.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: This is associated with intentional murder.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment that includes exile has to do with any grave mischief as contained in the Quran 5: 33.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The Islamic general formal legal code is what the religious group upholds.

– Yes

Notes: The legal code contained in the Quran is what the religious group believes in and adopts.

– Yes

Notes: The Quran is recognized as the first source of Islamic law. Thus, the religious group relies on what the Scripture enacts as the penal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, majority of the membership are not found in Shariah compliant places; they are being subjected to the customary legal code.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Through the government.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Indigenous languages like Yoruba, Hausa and international languages like English, and Arabic are being used by the religious group.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: The religious group adopts the Islamic lunar calendar and the Gregorian calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Poultry

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Ansar-ud-deen Society of Nigeria, Clarke, Peter B.. *West Africa and Islam: A Study of Religious Development from the 8th to the 20th Century*. London: Edward Arnold, 1982. p.225, 228. 248

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